

Spider assemblages associated with the umbrella thorn tree *Vachellia tortilis* (Forssk.) in South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae)

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ABSTRACT: A total of 112 spider species from 17 families were collected over three years from *Vachellia tortilis* (Forssk.) from two localities in the Limpopo and the KwaZulu-Natal provinces. From the farm Amsterdam near Dendron, 14 families represented by 68 species were sampled, and from the farm Vergeval near Pongola, 17 families and 79 species. Thirty species (26.5%) are recorded from both sites. The aim was to find out whether the same tree species host different spider communities.

Keywords: biodiversity, Savanna Biome, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA).

INTRODUCTION

Spiders occupy different field layers, such as the ground layer, grass and herb layer, and the tree layers, with web dwellers making their webs everywhere (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2024). Information is available on spider association with the soil surface (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2002; Janion-Scheepers *et al.*, 2016) and grass layer (Haddad *et al.*, 2013; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad, 2014), but a few papers were published on spiders associated with the tree layer in the savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011).

During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), several studies have investigated the habitat association of spiders to tree canopies. Tree species differ in their habitat characters and consequently support different spider assemblages (Southwood *et al.*, 1982, 2005). At the Nylsvley Nature Reserve in the Limpopo Province, spider assemblages were sampled from five tree species (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2009). Neethling & Haddad (2013) studied arboreal spider species from four tree species in the Free State, while Haddad (2016) reported on the spiders sampled from the bark of *Vachellia xanthophloea* from the Ndumo Game Reserve in KwaZulu-Natal. Several tree species were surveyed in the northern arid aspects of the Blouberg and Soutpansberg (Muelelwa *et al.*, 2010).

Another way to sample trees was to use a fogging apparatus. Spider assemblages were sampled fogging trees in orchards in agroecosystems such as avocado trees (*Persea americana*) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2005), macadamia nut trees (*Macadamia integrifolia*) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2005) and pistachio trees (*Pistacea vera*) (Haddad *et al.*, 2005). From citrus trees, spiders were sampled by beating and active search (Van den Berg *et al.*, 1992; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1998). Ten spider families were sampled using corrugated paper traps in commercial pine plantations near Sabie in Mpumalanga (Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1988).

In this paper, the spider assemblages sampled from *Vachellia tortilis* (Forssk.), also known as umbrella thorn, are discussed. The spiders were sampled during a 5-year project to determine the effect of Dieldrin cover spraying to control the harvester termite *Hodotermes mossambicus* (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1978). The aim was to find out whether the same tree species host different spider communities.

Vachellia tortilis is a medium-to-large, canopied tree native to areas in Africa and the Middle East. It is a hardy, deciduous, drought-resistant, slow-growing umbrella-shaped tree that can be 4–15 m tall. It often has several trunks but is usually reduced to a small, wiry shrub less than 1 m tall under arid conditions (Fig. 1). The tree bears two types of thorns (Fig. 2) and bears abundant, fragrant, white to yellow puffball flowers from November to January (Fig. 3), followed by distinctive curled pods (Fig. 4).

Figures 1–4. *Vachellia tortilis*. 1. The trees chosen to sample. 2. Branch with the white thorns. 3. White to yellow, puffball flowers. 4. Distinctive curled seed pods. Credits: Peter Webb.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study area and period: The surveys were undertaken at two sites (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1978).

1. Farm Amsterdam (23° 16'S; 29° 27'E), Soutpansberg district, ± 16 km NE of Dendron/ Mogwadi, Limpopo. Sampling took place between 1968 to 1970.
2. Farm Vergeval (27° 31' S; 31° 42' E), Ngotshe district, 11 km SSE of Pongola, KwaZulu-Natal. Sampling took place between 1967 to 1968.

Map showing the two sites 1. Farm Amsterdam, Dendron/Mogwadi. 2. Farm Vergeval, Pongola.

Sampling methods: Spiders were sampled using a beating tray and beating branches of the *V. tortilis* trees. Trees of approximately equal size and form were chosen randomly. Four branches on each tree were beaten 10 times, and the falling arthropods were caught on a square sheet measuring 0.8 m². The total catch from four trees (= 16 branches) constituted a sample (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1978).

Voucher specimens: The spiders sampled were preserved in 70% ethanol. Sorting and identifications were done in Pretoria at the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the ARC-Plant Health and Protection division, where the voucher specimens were deposited.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of 112 species, 69 genera, and 17 families have been collected from both sites (Table 3). The three most species-rich families are the Salticidae (25 spp.), followed by the Araneidae (24 spp.) and Thomisidae (23 spp.). Two families are represented by singletons.

Thirty species (26.5%) are recorded from both sites from 14 families. Three families, Deinopidae, Mimetidae, and Zodariidae, were only sampled from Pongola. Many specimens collected from the trees were immature.

DENDRON. Numbers present: A total of 68 species, 50 genera, and 14 families were recorded (Table 3). This was one of the first surveys undertaken in South Africa, and data was included in the review article of the Savanna Biome (Foord *et al.*, 2011).

Family diversity: Of the 14 spider families collected from Dendron (Table 3), the two most species-rich families are the Salticidae (18 spp.), followed by the Thomisidae (16 spp.) and Araneidae (12 spp.). Four families are represented by singletons.

PONGOLA. Numbers present: A total of 79 species, 53 genera, from 17 families, were recorded (Table 3). This was one of the first surveys undertaken in the KwaZulu-Natal, and data was included in the review article of the Savanna Biome (Foord *et al.*, 2011).

Family diversity: Of the 17 spider families collected from Pongola (Tables 3), the three most species-rich families are the Araneidae (23 spp.) Thomisidae (18 spp.) and Salticidae (14 spp.). Nine families are represented by singletons.

NEW SPECIES

The voucher material is deposited in the NCA and is available for taxonomic research. So far five species sampled from *V. tortilis* were newly described (Table 1).

Table 1: Species newly described from *Vachellia tortilis* trees at Pongola and Dendron.

PONGOLA		
Trachelidae	<i>Coronarachne denticulata</i>	Haddad & Lyle, 2024
Thomisidae	<i>Pherecydes carinae</i>	Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980
Thomisidae	<i>Pherecydes lucinae</i>	Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980
Zodariidae	<i>Thaumastochilus termitomimus</i>	Jocqué, 1994
DENDRON/MOGWADI		
Salticidae	<i>Menemerus meridionalis</i>	Wesołowska, 1999

Table 2: Spider families, genera (G) and species (SP.) and % of total sampled from *Vachellia tortilis* trees at Pongola and Dendron.

FAMILY	G	SP	%	FAMILY	G	SP	%
ARANEIDAE	13	24	0	SALTICIDAE	19	25	22.3
CHEIRACANTHIIDAE	2	4	3.6	SELENOPIIDAE	1	2	1.8
CLUBIONIDAE	1	3	2.7	SPARASSIDAE	2	2	1.8
DEINOPIDAE	2	2	1.8	TETRAGNATHIDAE	2	2	1.8
ERESIDAE	2	2	1.8	THERIDIIDAE	5	6	5.4
HERSILIIDAE	1	2	1.8	THOMISIDAE	12	23	20.5
MIMETIDAE	1	1	0.9	ULOBORIDAE	3	3	2.7
OXYOPIIDAE	3	7	6.3	ZODARIIDAE	1	1	0.9
PHILODROMIDAE	1	3	2.7	TOTAL	71	112	

SPECIES SAMPLED

The spiders sampled from *V. tortilis* trees are free-living plant dwellers and web dwellers. The plant dwellers 73 spp. (65.2%) are found on the bark, foliage, and flowers while the web dwellers 39 spp. (34.8%) use the tree branches to attach their webs. When inactive, they rest on the tree, usually the bark. Bark dwellers either live on the surface of the bark or in holes and cracks in or under the bark. They have a mottled appearance and are usually very well camouflaged, closely resembling pieces of bark. Their colour varies from greyish white to dark brown, and their bodies are frequently flattened or with knobs and spiny protuberances.

This survey confirmed that certain species can be considered typical tree dwellers. Some genera, like *Hersilia*, are only known from trees, but others are not so well known. In comparing the spider species collected from *V. tortilis* from the two sites with spider species sampled from five tree species in the Savanna Biome at Nylsvley Nature Reserve, Limpopo Province (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2009) several species were repeatedly sampled. The plant dwellers include *Hamataliwa kulczynskii* (Fig. 17), *Philodromus guineensis* (Fig. 19), *Afraflacilla altera* (Fig. 20), *Baryphas ahenus* (Fig. 21), *Tmarus africanus* (Fig. 33) and *Tmarus cameliformis* (Fig. 34).

However there are numerous species that differ. This correspond with the findings of Korenko *et al.* (2011) who found differences in spider assemblage in different tree species within the mixed forest of Central Europe.

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Araneidae *Argiope australis*

Araneidae *Caerostris corticosa*

Araneidae *Cyphalonotus larvatus*

Gasteracantha versicolor

Araneidae *Isoxya tabulata*

Araneidae *Neoscona subfusca*

Araneidae *Neoscona triangula*

Eresidae *Stegodyphus dumicola*

Cheiracanthiidae *Cheiracanthium africanum*

Cheiracanthium vansoni

Clubionidae *Clubiona africana*

Hersiliidae *Hersilia sericea*

Oxyopidae *Hamataliwa kulczynskii*

Philodromidae *Philodromus browningi*

Philodromidae *Philodromus guineensis*

Salticidae *Afraflacilla altera*

Salticidae *Baryphas ahenus*

Salticidae *Myrmarachne ichneumon*

Figures 5–22. Web dwellers (5-12) and free-living plant dwellers (13-22) sampled from *Vachellia xanthophloea* from Dendron and Pongola. Credits: Peter Webb.

Salticidae *Portia schultzi*

Salticidae *Thyene inflata*

Salticidae *Thyene natalii*

Salticidae *Tusitala barbata*

Thomisidae *Heriades crassispinus*

Thomisidae *Misumenops rubrodecoratus*

Thomisidae *Simorcus cotti*

Thomisidae *Synema decens*

Thomisidae *Synema imitatrix*

Thomisidae *Thomisus scrupeus*

Thomisidae *Tmarus africanus*

Thomisidae *Tmarus cameliformis*

Thomisidae *Tmarus comellinii*

Thomisidae *Tmarus longicaudatus*

Figures 23–36. Free-living plant dwelling spiders sampled from *Vachellia xanthophloea* from Dendron and Pongola. Credits: Peter Webb except 36. Stefan Foord.

TABLE 3: Spider species and their guilds (WB web dweller; FPD free living plant dwellers) sampled from *Vachellia tortilis* during surveys at the farm Vergeval district Ngotshe near Pongola (P) and the farm Amsterdam, Dendron (D).

SPECIES	GUILD	P	D	SPECIES	GUILD	P	D
1. ARANEIDAE				9. PHILODROMIDAE			
<i>Araneus apricus</i> (Karsch, 1884)	WB	1	0	<i>Hamataliwa rufocaligata</i> Simon, 1898 (Fig. 37)	FPD	0	1
<i>Argiope australis</i> (Walckenaer, 1805) (Fig. 5)	WB	1	1	<i>Oxyopes jacksoni</i> Lessert, 1915	FPD	1	0
<i>Argiope flavipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	WB	1	0	<i>Oxyopes longispinosus</i> Lawrence, 1938	FPD	1	0
<i>Argiope trifasciata</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	WB	1	0	<i>Oxyopes</i> sp. 3	FPD	0	1
<i>Caerostris corticosa</i> Pocock, 1902 (Fig. 6)	WB	1	1	<i>Peucetia striata</i> Karsch, 1878	FPD	0	1
<i>Caerostris sexcuspidata</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	WB	1	0	<i>Peucetia transvaalica</i> Simon, 1896	FPD	0	1
<i>Caerostris vicina</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	WB	1	0	10. SALTICIDAE			
<i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834)	WB	1	0	<i>Afraflacilla altera</i> (Wesolowska, 2000) (Fig. 20)	FPD	1	1
<i>Cyphalonotus larvatus</i> (Simon, 1881) (Fig. 7)	WB	1	1	<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902 (Fig. 21)	FPD	1	1
<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	WB	0	1	<i>Dendryphantès hararensis</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	FPD	1	0
<i>Gasteracantha milvoides</i> Butler, 1873	WB	1	0	<i>Evarcha ignea</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	FPD	0	1
<i>Gasteracantha versicolor</i> (Walckenaer, 1841) (Fig. 8)	WB	1	1	<i>Harmochirus luculentus</i> Simon, 1886	FPD	1	0
<i>Hypsacantha crucimaculata</i> (Dahl, 1914)	WB	1	0	<i>Heliophanus pistaciae</i> Wesolowska, 2003	FPD	0	1
<i>Isoxya cicatricosa</i> (C.L. Koch, 1844)	WB	1	0	<i>Hyllus argyrotoxis</i> Simon, 1902	FPD	1	0
<i>Isoxya tabulata</i> (Thorell, 1859) (Fig. 9)	WB	1	1	<i>Hyllus treleaveni</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	FPD	1	0
<i>Neoscona blondeli</i> (Simon, 1886)	WB	1	1	<i>Icius insolidus</i> (Wesolowska, 1999)	FPD	0	1
<i>Neoscona moreli</i> (Vinson, 1863)	WB	1	0	<i>Langona bisecta</i> Lawrence, 1927	FPD	0	1
<i>Neoscona rufipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	WB	1	0	<i>Langona hirsuta</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011	FPD	0	1
<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837) (Fig. 10)	WB	1	1	<i>Langona warchalowskii</i> Wesolowska, 2007	FPD	0	1
<i>Neoscona triangula</i> (Keyserling, 1864) (Fig. 11)	WB	1	1	<i>Menemerus meridionalis</i> Wesolowska, 1999	FPD	0	1
<i>Nephilingis cruentata</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	WB	0	1	<i>Mogrus albogularis</i> Simon, 1901	FPD	0	1
<i>Singa lawrencei</i> (Lessert, 1930)	WB	1	0	<i>Myrmarachne ichneumon</i> (Simon, 1886) (Fig. 22)	FPD	1	1
<i>Trichonephila senegalensis annulata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	WB	0	1	<i>Myrmarachne lulengana</i> Roewer, 1965	FPD	1	0
<i>Trichonephila inaurata madagascariensis</i> (Vinson, 1863)	WB	1	0	<i>Parajotus obscurolfemoratus</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	FPD	0	1
2. CHEIRACANTHIDAE				<i>Portia schultzi</i> Karsch, 1878 (Fig. 23)	FPD	1	1
<i>Cheiracanthium africanum</i> Lessert, 1921 (Fig. 13)	FPD	1	1	<i>Rhene machadoi</i> Berland & Millot, 1941	FPD	0	1
<i>Cheiracanthium furculatum</i> Karsch, 1879	FPD	1	0	<i>Rumburak laxus</i> (Zhang & Maddison, 2012)	FPD	0	1
<i>Cheiracanthium vansoni</i> Lawrence, 1936 (Fig. 14)	FPD	1	1	<i>Thyene coccineovittata</i> (Simon, 1886)	FPD	1	0
<i>Cheiramiona paradisis</i> Lotz, 2003	FPD	1	0	<i>Thyene inflata</i> (Gerstäcker, 1873) (Fig. 24)	FPD	1	1
3. CLUBIONIDAE				<i>Thyene natalii</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903 (Fig. 25)	FPD	1	1
<i>Clubiona africana</i> Lessert, 1921 (Fig. 15)	FPD	1	1	<i>Thyene ogdeni</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	FPD	1	0
<i>Clubiona bevisi</i> Lessert, 1923	FPD	0	1	<i>Tusitala barbata</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902 (Fig. 26)	FPD	1	1
<i>Clubiona pongolensis</i> Lawrence, 1952	FPD	1	0	11. SELENOPIIDAE			
4. DEINOPIIDAE				<i>Selenops radiatus</i> Latreille, 1819	FPD	1	0
<i>Asianopsis cylindrica</i> (Pocock, 1898)	WB	1	0	<i>Selenops kruegeri</i> Lawrence, 1940	FPD	0	1
<i>Menneus camelus</i> Pocock, 1902	WB	1	0	12. SPARASSIDAE			
5. ERESIDAE				<i>Olios chelifera</i> Lawrence, 1937	FPD	1	0
<i>Gandanameno fumosa</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	WB	0	1	<i>Palystes leroyorum</i> Croeser, 1996	FPD	0	1
<i>Stegodyphus dumicola</i> Pocock, 1898 (Fig. 12)	WB	1	1	13. TETRAGNATHIDAE			
6. HERSILIIDAE				<i>Leucauge festiva</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	WB	1	0
<i>Hersilia sericea</i> Pocock, 1898 (Fig. 16)	FPD	1	1	<i>Tetragnatha bogotensis</i> Keyserling, 1865	WB	0	1
<i>Hersilia setifrons</i> Lawrence, 1928	FPD	1	0				
7. MIMETIDAE							
<i>Mimetus cornutus</i> Lawrence, 1947	FPD	1	0				
8. OXYOPIIDAE							
<i>Hamataliwa kulczynskii</i> (Lessert, 1915) (Fig. 17)	FPD	1	1				

SPECIES	GUILD	P	D
14. THERIDIIDAE			
<i>Anelosimus nelsoni</i> Agnarsson, 2006	WB	1	0
<i>Argyrodes convivans</i> Lawrence, 1937	WB	1	0
<i>Argyrodes zonatus</i> (Walckenaer, 1841)	WB	0	1
<i>Enoplognatha molesta</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	WB	0	1
<i>Episinus bilineatus</i> Simon, 1894	WB	1	0
<i>Phycosoma martinae</i> (Roberts, 1983)	WB	1	0
15. THOMISIDAE			
<i>Diaea puncta</i> Karsch, 1884	FPD	1	1
<i>Heriaeus crassispinus</i> Lawrence, 1942 (Fig. 27)	FPD	1	1
<i>Heriaeus transvaalicus</i> Simon, 1895	FPD	0	1
<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1942 (Fig. 28)	FPD	1	1
<i>Mystaria savannensis</i> Lewis & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014	FPD	0	1
<i>Oxytate argenteooculata</i> (Simon, 1886)	FPD	1	1
<i>Pherecydes carinae</i> Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980	FPD	1	0
<i>Pherecydes lucinae</i> Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980	FPD	1	0
<i>Pherecydes zebra</i> Lawrence, 1927	FPD	0	1
<i>Phrynarachne melloleitaoi</i> Lessert, 1933	FPD	1	0
<i>Simorcus cotti</i> Lessert, 1936 (Fig. 29)	FPD	1	1
<i>Sylligma ndumi</i> Lewis & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2011	FPD	1	0
<i>Synema decens</i> (Karsch, 1878) (Fig. 30)	FPD	1	1
<i>Synema imitatrix</i> (Pavesi, 1883) (Fig. 31)	FPD	1	1
<i>Thomisus blandus</i> Karsch, 1880 (Fig. 38)	FPD	1	0
<i>Thomisus congoensis</i> Comellini, 1957	FPD	0	1
<i>Thomisus scrupeus</i> (Simon, 1886) (Fig. 32)	FPD	1	1
<i>Thomisus stenningi</i> Pocock, 1900	FPD	0	1
<i>Tmarus africanus</i> Lessert, 1919 (Fig. 33)	FPD	1	1
<i>Tmarus cameliformis</i> Millot, 1942 (Fig. 34)	FPD	1	1
<i>Tmarus comellinii</i> Garcia-Neto, 1989 (Fig. 35)	FPD	1	1
<i>Tmarus foliatus</i> Lessert, 1928	FPD	1	0
<i>Tmarus longicaudatus</i> Millot, 1942 (Fig. 36)	FPD	1	1
16. ULOBORIDAE			
<i>Hyptiotes akermani</i> Wiehle, 1964	WD	1	0
<i>Miagrammopes brevicaudus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1882	WD	0	1
<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas, 1846	WD	0	1
17. ZODARIIDAE			
<i>Thaumastochilus termitomimus</i> Jocqué, 1994	FPD	1	0
	TOTAL	79	68

Hamataliwa rufocaligata from Dendron (Stefan Foord)

Thomisus blandus from Pongolaa (Peter Webb)